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David Martínez Zorrilla

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On the link between consistency and conflict in normative systems

David Martínez Zorrilla

1 Introduction

- 1 In a broad sense, a normative conflict is a situation in which at least two normative (moral, legal, religious, social, etc.) requirements apply, but the agent (or one who is otherwise responsible for applying those requirements) cannot satisfy them all because satisfying one means that at least one of the others cannot be satisfied, and vice versa. The agent ought to do x and also ought to do y , but doing x prevents the agent from doing y , and doing y makes it impossible to do x .
- 2 In recent decades much attention in both legal theory and moral philosophy has been devoted to the question of normative conflicts, and for good reason. If one of the primary purposes of a normative system is to guide the behaviour of the agents subject to that system, and the system does so by stating what we ought to do or refrain from doing, then agents will find themselves in a situation of normative conflict whenever incompatible requirements apply to them.¹ No course of action will satisfy all these requirements, so the agent will act wrongly (will be non-compliant) no matter what she choose to do. This seems to suggest, at least *prima facie*, the existence of some kind of failure or defect in the normative system, as it cannot be a guide for the agent in deciding what to. Moreover, if we assume that for a decision or course of action to be legally or morally justified, it needs to at least not to be incompatible with what the relevant normative system requires, situations of conflict also pose a problem when it comes to rationally *justifying* our decisions.
- 3 Normative conflicts have been widely addressed in both moral philosophy (moral dilemmas)² and legal theory (antinomies). But there seem to be some differences in the way this problem is generally addressed in each field. In the debate on moral conflicts and dilemmas, the discussion has been focused on the very *possibility* of moral conflicts and on the problems these situations might imply for the agent, such as how to

determine which alternative course of action should prevail over the remaining incompatible ones, or what responsibility derives from unattended duties. This approach could be regarded as *pragmatic*, as its focus is on *agents* and what they *ought to do*, and only in relation to these questions does the theoretical question about the consistency of the normative system become relevant (by arguing that a situation of moral conflict results from an inconsistency in the moral system and/or can be solved by reframing the system in order to make it consistent).³

- 4 In legal theory, on the other hand, the debate about antinomies is mainly focused on the consistency or inconsistency of the legal system itself, with the agent's decision-making becoming an afterthought in that only subsequently does the problem emerge of what the inconsistencies of a legal system might mean for an agent's ability to determine what the system requires of the agent.⁴
- 5 Either way, analysing the links between the consistency of a normative system and the normative conflicts the system may give rise to remains a question of both theoretical and practical interest.⁵ In short, if a system's logical inconsistency is a necessary condition for a normative conflict to arise—i.e., every conflict is owed to a logical inconsistency within the system (what I call a “system inconsistency”)—then all potential conflicts could, in theory, be avoided by building perfectly consistent systems⁶. If, on the other hand, conflicts can arise even within the framework of perfectly consistent systems, it would follow that conflicts and dilemmas are an inescapable feature⁷ of our legal and moral practices, and there is no way to eradicate them once and for all (even if this wouldn't necessarily mean that consistency, or the lack of it, is irrelevant to conflicts and dilemmas).⁸
- 6 Although authors have offered several different definitions and drawn divergent classifications,⁹ to not prejudge the links between conflicts and consistency, it is advisable to use a *pragmatic* notion of normative conflict, one according to which we as normative subjects, in von Wright's terminology,¹⁰ find ourselves in a normative conflict whenever we are not empirically able to satisfy the demands imposed by all the norms applicable to the case at hand (i.e., we cannot comply with all the applicable obligations), because satisfying any one of the conflicting norms precludes satisfying the others.¹¹ That is, the very fact of satisfying one of the applicable norms makes the others unsatisfiable. So, in a first (and still provisional, as will be shown later) definition, a normative conflict could be defined as *any situation in which at least two norms apply to an agent, but the agent cannot (empirically) comply with them all (joint compliance is impossible),¹² because compliance with any one of these norms (taken individually) makes it (empirically) impossible to comply with all the rest.*
- 7 It seems *prima facie* quite reasonable to assert that practical conflicts or dilemmas are impossible if the normative system from which the relative obligations derive is logically consistent (*obligationes non colliduntur*), just like, by analogy, a consistent set of propositions cannot entail a contradiction (such that a normative conflict would be a symptom of an inconsistency in the set of norms, and may even count as proof of such an inconsistency). In fact, this idea has been embraced by some prominent philosophers.¹³ Nevertheless, Ruth B. Marcus, in a seminal paper,¹⁴ challenged this assumption and put forward some arguments to show that conflicts and dilemmas are possible even in the context of a consistent set of rules or principles. In what follows, I evaluate whether Marcus's contention is correct and, if so, whether it is correct for the reasons she lays out.

2 Normative conflicts as a result of system inconsistencies

- 9 A normative system is consistent if, and only if, it contains no antinomies or deontic contradictions,¹⁵ such that a normative contradiction or antinomy within the system makes it inconsistent.¹⁶ Many authors seem to agree that whenever two or more norms are jointly or collectively applicable to a case and their application leads to a deontic contradiction, a normative conflict arises, since it is logically impossible for a normative subject to comply with them all (i.e., to make true the set of propositions connected to all the applicable norms at stake).
- 10 Situations of deontic contradiction or antinomy, at least when the deontic operators of obligation (O) and prohibition (Ph) are involved, seem to entail a normative conflict. To illustrate this idea, I will use a classic example from Carlos E. Alchourrón.¹⁷ Let us suppose that an authority enacts these two norms:

(N₁) It is obligatory to stop at a traffic light on red.

(N₂) It is forbidden to stop in a military zone.

- 11 If we symbolize the action ‘stop’ as ‘p’, an antinomy or deontic contradiction will arise whenever an agent finds herself before a red light in a military zone: According to norm N₁, she ought to stop [‘O(p)’], while under norm N₂ she ought not to do so [‘Ph(p)’]. In this predicament, there seems to be no way to escape a normative conflict,¹⁸ since no matter what she does, she will break one of the norms: If she stops, she will break norm N₂, and if she does not stop, she will be breaking norm N₁. Compliance with both norms would imply the truth of the propositions ‘The agent stops’ and ‘The agent does not stop’, which is logically (and therefore also empirically) impossible, so therefore a normative conflict arises.
- 12 It should be highlighted that norms N₁ and N₂ are not inconsistent *per se*, but a *normative system* containing both norms is an inconsistent system, in the previously stated terms. This can be formally demonstrated using Alchourrón and Bulygin’s model for the analysis of normative systems.¹⁹ Despite the model being quite sophisticated, making it is beyond the scope of this paper to provide a detailed explanation of it, explicating some of its fundamental concepts will be useful to help illustrate the problem.
- 13 As previously stated, a normative system is regarded as inconsistent if and only if it contains at least one antinomy or deontic contradiction. Antinomies are referred to as *generic cases* of the system. Generic cases are logical classes defined by the presence or absence of the different *relevant properties* of the norms of the system. A relevant property is a condition (situation, object, event, etc.) the presence or absence of which is taken into account by the norms of the system to determine the deontic qualification of an action/behaviour). In the case of the normative set formed by N₁ and N₂, the relevant properties are the presence (or absence) of a traffic light on red (‘R’) and the presence (or absence) of a military zone (‘M’). The set of all the relevant properties of a

normative system is the Universe of Properties (UP). The UP determines the total number of different possible generic cases of the system (the Universe of Cases or UC), because the UC contains all the logically possible combinations of the presence and absence of the elements of the UP, excluding the tautological and contradictory ones. The total number of cases is 2^n , where 'n' stands for the number or elements of the UP. In the example, there are only two properties or UP elements, so there are 4 (2^2) generic cases: 1) R & M (a red traffic light in a military zone); 2) R & -M (a red traffic light in a non-military zone); 3) -R & M (not a red traffic light in a military zone); and 4) -R & -M (not a red traffic light in a non-military zone). Norm N_1 applies whenever property 'R' is present (cases 1 and 2), whereas norm N_2 applies whenever property 'M' is present (cases 1 and 3). This entails that in case 1 (red traffic light and military zone), both N_1 and N_2 apply, and as long as N_1 imposes 'O(p)' and N_2 imposes 'Ph(p)', an antinomy or deontic contradiction [O(p) & Ph(p), which entails P(p) & -P(p)] arises, making the system inconsistent in the defined terms. Moreover, whenever an instance of generic case 1 occurs, there will be a normative conflict, as it is conceptually impossible to satisfy both N_1 and N_2 , and the satisfaction of either of them prevents the possibility of complying with the other.

- 14 A very interesting consequence of inconsistent normative systems due to antinomies or deontic contradictions is that they make normative conflicts foreseeable or predictable: there is no need to wait for an actual (empirical) situation of someone being in front of a red traffic light in a military zone to know that the agent will face a normative conflict. The conflict is, using Guastini's words,²⁰ *in abstracto* (as opposed to *in concreto* conflicts, which would depend entirely on the specific empirical circumstances of the individual case).
- 15 Nevertheless, some authors, such as Feis,²¹ challenge this statement and claim that those kind of situations are better conceived as *in concreto* conflicts, i.e., non 'predictable' because for the conflict to arise certain empirical facts must be present (no conflict arises unless someone finds herself in front of a red traffic light in a military zone), and it's not possible to foresee or predict when (or if) that situation will happen. Ultimately, according to Feis, normative conflicts would depend on empirical facts. The main argument, in sum, is that for a conflict to arise certain *facts* have always to occur, and the empirical and contingent nature of those facts make conflicts (almost) *unpredictable*. Even in Alchourrón's example, someone must find themselves in front of a red traffic light in a military zone, and this is a contingent and (mostly) unpredictable fact.
- 16 Although Feis has an interesting point, the argument does not work as intended because two different senses of 'predictability' seem to be used here, which we could refer to as predictability in a conceptual sense (predictability₁) and predictability in an epistemic sense (predictability₂), respectively. In the first sense, to say that certain event is predictable₁ is to claim that a *certain class, kind, or type of a situation/event* will take place as a result or consequence of certain previous conditions, *also defined or described in generic terms*. On the other hand, for a certain event to be predictable₂ is to claim that certain event *x* with a specific empirical existence will take place in moment *m*.
- 17 For instance, I can predict₁ that if my pencil rolls off the edge of the table, it will fall to the floor due to gravity, even if I usually cannot predict₂ when and where a pencil will fall (if it ever does). Or, for example, speaking about the effects of global warming,

certain consequences like an increase of average temperatures, or of the sea level, or of the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events are predictable₁, although we cannot predict₂ when and where the first torrential rains and floods of the year 2050 will take place.

- 18 Generic cases are not facts, but logical classes. For that reason, they do not depend on empirical or factual circumstances, but rather on the very logical structure of the system. A generic case might be *empirically void* (for instance, there could be no traffic lights in military zones), but this does not mean that the system is consistent nor that there is an absence of a conceptual link between that inconsistency and the emergence of a conflict. This is because conceptually, in any logically possible world, we can predict₁ a conflict whenever those conditions of application are met, i.e., when both norms are jointly applicable. In other words, while the actual occurrence of the individual case of a red light in a military zone is “factual” or contingent, the logical incompatibility and the emergence of a normative conflict is conceptual or necessary. Antinomies are, using an analogy, like the property of ‘fragility’ of glass: A piece of glass might not ever break as a matter of fact, but this does not mean that it's not fragile nor that it will not necessarily break if certain conditions are met.²²
- 19 As a result of what has been argued thus far, inconsistencies within a normative system could be considered, if not as proof, at least as a *sign* or indication of a conceptual link (as a sufficient condition) between normative inconsistency and situations of conflict. However, this conclusion has been challenged by some authors who point out that not all normative inconsistencies give rise to a situation of conflict. That is because if we adopt the pragmatic definition of ‘normative conflict’ previously introduced (a definition having to do with the impossibility of joint compliance, where a set of legal or moral norms cannot all be complied with) no conflict emerges when one of these norms is a permission. Although in most deontic logic models the statements “O(p)” and “P-(p)” are contradictory, since “O(p)” entails “-P-(p)”, it seems possible for an agent to do an action, ‘p’, that does not infringe any of the norms. The same can be said in cases involving a prohibition or a permission. To give an example: If a norm prohibits smoking in a particular place [‘Ph(p)’], while another allows smoking [‘P(p)’], there is a course of conduct following which an agent would not infringe either of these norms, namely, not smoking.
- 20 Because of this (apparent, at least) asymmetry between mandates (obligations and prohibitions) and permissions, some philosophers²³ claim that conflicts between a mandate and a permission are different in kind from conflicts between mandates, while others refuse to consider the former as conflict situations at all²⁴ because, strictly speaking, permissions can neither be complied with nor violated.²⁵
- 21 Since there must be a mandate (an obligation or prohibition) if we are to be able to talk about compliance or non-compliance, the only cases in which, for logical reasons, two norms cannot be jointly complied with are conflicts between mandates. If a mandate and a permission come into play, only one of these two norms can be an object of compliance or non-compliance, and so there cannot be a normative conflict, since a normative conflict has been defined in terms of *compliance* with the norms in question.
- 22 Perhaps this position is best illustrated by means of a metaphorical example. Let us think of human behaviour as the activity of crossing doorways. Whenever we carry out a particular action, we cross a doorway, stepping out of one room and walking into an adjacent one. Each door in a room represents one of the generic behaviours (an action/

omission) regulated by the normative system in a given context. The norms thus determine how many doors are in any one room and whether these doors are open or closed. For instance, if in room 1 the system only regulates action 'p', then there will be only two doors, namely, 'p' and '-p'. The deontic operator 'P' (permitted) means that the corresponding door is open, while its negation, '-P', means that it is closed. In this way, if we are in room 1 and a norm says that this case triggers the normative consequence 'O(p)', the system establishes that door 'p' is open, while all the doors that are not 'p' (in this case only '-p') are closed.²⁶ Consequently, under this system, we have no alternative other than to cross through door 'p'. If the applicable norms in room 1 regulated behaviours 'p' and 'q', there would be four doors: 'p & q', 'p & -q', '-p & q', and '-p & -q'. The total number of doors therefore depends on the total number of actions/omissions regulated by the norms applicable to the case (room) in question.²⁷

- 23 When a normative system contains an antinomy, that would be like saying that one or more doors in the room are at the same time open and closed. If, for instance, for one and the same 'room' the system yields solutions 'F(p)'²⁸ and 'Ph(p)'—given that 'F(p)' entails 'P(p)' and 'Ph(p)' entails '-P(p)'—door 'p' would be both open and closed. In this door analogy, when a mandate and a permission are involved, authors for whom this does not give rise to any conflict can be said to pay no attention to whether any doors are simultaneously open and closed; they are instead focused on *whether the room has any open doors*. In the example, since door '-p' remains open ['P(-p)' is entailed by both 'F(p)' and 'Ph(p)'], there would be no problem at all. Only in a conflict of mandates would we find that the doors are all closed.
- 24 At this point, in determining whether a conceptual link exists between inconsistency and conflicts, we have to choose among three alternative stances: (a) accept the previous reasoning and conclude that inconsistency is not a sufficient condition for a conflict, as shown by the case of permissions; (b) claim that even permissions can be complied with (that it makes logical sense to treat them as objects of compliance or non-compliance); or (c) modify our definition of 'normative conflict' to make room for permissions.²⁹ I will argue in favour of alternative (c), since (a) and (b) both prove to be inadequate.
- 25 Let us see why that might be, starting with alternative (b). It would be quite odd, even in the context of a natural language such as English, to say that we should "comply with" a permission. Even though permissions arguably guide conduct, giving us justification for our behaviour as agents subject to a permission, they do not seem to work like obligations and prohibitions. For this reason, it seems more plausible to instead say that permissions can be *made use of or exercised*, but not "complied with."³⁰
- 26 Nor does alternative (a) seem satisfactory. Even if we grant that permissions cannot properly be 'complied with' (they are not a proper object of compliance or non-compliance), that does not deprive them of deontic force or meaning: We will still have to accept that when an act or course of conduct is marked as 'permitted', this means that, from a deontic point of view, the act may be carried out or the conduct engaged in as an open course of action.³¹ So, if the same action is simultaneously qualified as prohibited and permitted, this is like saying that this course of action, in deontic terms, is simultaneously open and closed, and this is usually regarded as a normative conflict. If an act is (deontically) permitted, the agent has a legitimate claim to carry out that act, even when another norm prohibits it and precludes that same possibility. It seems

more reasonable, then, to label situations of this kind as normative conflicts than to treat them as non-conflictive.

- 27 The most powerful argument I can think of in support of alternative (c)—and so in support of a more capacious definition of ‘normative conflict’, a modified one encompassing permissions—is that of *effectiveness*. Effectiveness can be predicated of prescriptions but not of assertive statements (propositions), which can be true or false. Indeed, the notions of truth and effectiveness are conceptually linked, since any prescriptive statement can be paired with a corresponding assertive one.³² For instance, for the prescription ‘Jones, close the door!’, we would have the corresponding assertive statement ‘Jones closed the door’. The prescription is said to be effective when the corresponding assertive statement is true, and ineffective when it is false.³³ Therefore, the concept of effectiveness is parasitic on that of truth, as the latter depends on the former.³⁴
- 28 Most of the prescriptive norms in our legal and moral systems are structured as universal prescriptions, in the sense that they are addressed to *classes* of subjects (agents), for they state that in situations that display certain *properties*, certain *generic* actions must be performed. For this reason, a mandate will be effective when all the normative subjects—under the relevant conditions for applying the norm (its “opportunity”)³⁵— behave in such a way as to make true the proposition connected to that norm (for instance, the norm “Passengers must fasten their seat belts” is effective when the corresponding proposition “All passengers have their seat belts fastened” is true, that is, when *all* passengers *always* have their seat belts fastened). In the same way, a prohibitive norm like “Smoking in the classroom is not allowed” is effective whenever the proposition “No one is smoking in the classroom” is true or when *no one ever* smokes in the classroom. The norm will, by contrast, be ineffective in any other case.
- 29 When it comes to permissive norms, however, it is difficult to determine the circumstances under which they are effective or ineffective. Even so, von Wright plausibly argues that a permission is effective if the state of affairs permitted by the norm obtains (or ‘is the case’) at some time in the history of the norm, that is, if there exist at least one occasion on which the corresponding proposition is true.³⁶ In this way, a norm such as “Smoking in the classroom is allowed” is effective if at least one person has smoked in the classroom over the arc of the norm’s history. This seems quite sound, as we would think that a permission is effective if, and only if, someone has actually made use of it (if there are at least some occasions on which the permitted behaviour or state of affairs can actually be verified), for otherwise it would be as if the norm never existed.
- 30 If we accept this, then it is obvious that in cases involving deontic incompatibility between a mandate and a permission, it is logically impossible for the two norms to be jointly effective. If we take the norms “Smoking in the classroom is prohibited” and “Smoking in the classroom is allowed”, we should see that, necessarily, they can each be effective only at the expense of the other’s ineffectiveness. Thus, if the prohibitive norm is effective (the proposition “No one ever smoked in the classroom” is true), the permissive norm will be ineffective (the proposition “Someone smoked in the classroom” is false), and vice versa. As the two propositions contradict each other, they can never be both true. Of course, we are very far from a deontically perfect world,³⁷ and most legal and moral norms are, strictly speaking, ineffective. Nevertheless, this is

not quite relevant from a theoretical point of view, because the point is that those norms could *logically* be effective insofar the system is consistent. On the other hand, if the system is inconsistent, regardless of whether it contains only mandates or mandates and permissions, it will be logically impossible for all the norms to be jointly effective: the conjunction will be ineffective no matter the circumstances, and this holds regardless of whether it only contains mandates or if it also contains permissions. Therefore, it would not seem reasonable to frame the concept of normative conflict in such a way as to exclude situations of incompatibility between a mandate and a permission, treating these situations as logical consistencies.

- 31 As a conclusion, the concept of ‘normative conflict’ should be broadened to make room for situations of incompatibility between mandates and permissions. Thus a more refined definition of ‘normative conflict’ would be as follows: *A normative conflict is either: (a) a situation in which at least two mandates apply to an agent, but the agent cannot (empirically) comply with them all, as compliance with any one of these norms (taken individually) makes it impossible to comply with one or more of the others; or (b) a situation in which at least one mandate and one permission apply to an agent, but the agent cannot (empirically) comply with or exercise them all, as compliance with any one of the mandates (taken individually) makes it impossible to exercise one or more of the permissions, and vice versa (exercising any one of these permissions makes it impossible to comply with one or more of the mandates).*
- 32 We can therefore conclude that a normative system’s logical inconsistency is a *sufficient condition* for a normative conflict to arise. A consequence of this conclusion is that *at least some* normative conflicts could be avoided if it were possible to construct perfectly consistent normative systems.

3 Normative conflicts without inconsistency: The position of Ruth B. Marcus

- 33 Even assuming that a normative inconsistency will necessarily lead to a normative conflict—or that whenever incompatible norms are applicable to a case, a normative conflict will result—does not prove that *every* normative conflict is the result of a logical inconsistency in the normative system. That is, we still have to examine whether (a) inconsistency is not only a sufficient condition for a conflict but also a *necessary* one, or whether (b), on the contrary, a conflict can arise within a *consistent* normative system. If we found even a single example of this latter situation, the thesis of a necessary link between conflicts and inconsistency would be refuted.
- 34 As already stated, it is widely held that situations of conflict reveal a system to be inconsistent. But there are some who argue that not all conflicts are owed to a logical flaw in the system. Rather, at least some conflicts are owed to empirical circumstances (which may or may not be under the agent’s control).
- 35 As far as I know, the first author to make a theoretical account of the possibility of conflicts even within a consistent system was Thomas Aquinas. Aquinas distinguished between “dilemmas *simpliciter*”, in which an agent, without having violated any moral precept, is nonetheless bound by duty to simultaneously do and refrain from doing something, a situation revealing an inconsistency within the system, and “dilemmas *secundum quid*”,³⁸ which originate from a prior violation of a moral duty. The latter

would occur, for example, if while under a monogamous moral code like as a Christian ethic, we promised to marry two different people. This would obligate us to marry each one, but since no such arrangement would be permitted under such a code, we would be forced to breach the duty we owe to one of the two to whom we committed ourselves to marriage. Dilemmas *secundum quid* can therefore arise even within the framework of consistent systems, but with the necessary condition of a previous breach of a moral duty, so the dilemma or conflict cannot be attributed to a flaw inherent in the system but has to be blamed on the agent.³⁹ This position, then, opens the door to the possibility of conflicts owed to empirical circumstances.

- 36 In any case, Aquinas's claim is very limited in that it does not seem to contemplate a scenario wherein a conflict is owed not to an agent's decision to act in one way or another but to a series of unfortunate circumstances beyond the agent's control. Leap forward to the twentieth century, however, and we see authors who do point out the possibility of conflicts that do not necessarily come down to an inconsistency in the system. Among these, I will focus on Ruth B. Marcus,⁴⁰ who argues that there is no necessary link tying moral conflicts or dilemmas to the inconsistency of a moral system (that is, to the set of principles, duties, and other moral directives that define our moral obligations).⁴¹ There are two main theses that can be highlighted in Marcus's position, which I will refer to as the "obeyability thesis" and the "single-principle thesis." Let us take them up in turn.

3.1 The obeyability thesis

- 37 The notion of an 'obeyable' set of norms is key to Marcus's definition of a consistent normative system (or a "set of rules," in her own words). Using this definition of consistency, she argues that conflicts are possible even within a consistent normative system.
- 38 The obeyability thesis can be expressed as follows: a set of propositions is consistent if, and only if, it is logically possible for all the members of that set to be true, that is, if, and only if, a world can logically exist in which the conjunction of all these propositions is true. Thus, using her own example, the set of propositions "Snow is green" and "Grass is white" is consistent because even though the two propositions are false in *our* world, it is still logically possible for there to be a world in which they are both true.⁴² This would not be so if the propositions were "Snow is white" and "Snow is not white", since there is no possible world in which these propositions can both be true. The two propositions therefore form an inconsistent set.
- 39 Analogously, Marcus claims that a set of rules (norms) is consistent if, and only if, all its elements are *obeyable* in some possible world in all circumstances in that world. She illustrates this idea using the example of a simple two-player card game in which the two players take turns drawing one card from the top of the deck and revealing it, until all the cards are played out, and the winner is the player with the highest number of tricks. There are only two rules in force: (1) Black cards trump red cards; and (2) higher-valued cards trump lower-valued cards. In this game a conflict will arise whenever a red card is drawn whose value is higher than that of a black card. Under the first rule, the black card wins; under the second, the red one wins. However, Marcus argues, the system is *not* inconsistent, since there could be a world in which no black cards of higher value than red ones ever appear, so the conflict never arises. There

would be inconsistency only if the set of rules were not obeyable in *any* possible world under *any* circumstance. As a corollary, “a set of rules is inconsistent if there are *no* circumstances, no possible world, in which all the rules are satisfiable”.⁴³ If this were the case, the inconsistent rules would provide no guide for action under any circumstance.

- 40 Marcus’s argument is undoubtedly insightful and interesting, but it doesn’t seem to work quite as intended. Indeed, it puts us in a sort of a double bind: Either (1) the concept of obeyability works in a manner analogous to that of truth in working out the consistency of a system—i.e., just as we can test the consistency of a set of *propositions* by the metric of their truth, so too we can test the consistency of a set of *norms* by considering whether they are obeyable—but then the example does not illustrate the possibility of conflicts within a consistent normative system because the card game’s set of rules is inconsistent (i.e., it is not obeyable); or (2) Marcus uses a stipulative concept of obeyability that could be described as peculiar.
- 41 More specifically, it will be argued that a) the card game example is not adequate to illustrate Marcus’ argument because it is not a normative system in a strict sense (3.1.1) and its structure is assimilable to Alchourrón’s example, thus being an inconsistent system (3.1.2); and b) Marcus’ concept of ‘obeyability’ is questionable (3.1.3).
- 42 (3.1.1) In providing an example of a ‘set of rules’ (as opposed to a set of propositions), it’s quite surprising that Marcus refers to the rules of a game instead of using other kinds of norms more common in a moral or legal context (prescriptions). In a moral or legal normative system, the elements at stake are usually statements that set deontic qualifications of actions or behaviours (i.e., qualify certain actions as obligatory, prohibited, or permitted under certain conditions), and these are referred to as “prescriptions” or “prescriptive norms”. Instead, the ‘norms’ that apply to a card game (or to any other game in general) are instead conceptual or definitory rules, using von Wright’s terminology.⁴⁴ Those kinds of “norms” do not impose obligations, prohibitions, or permissions in a strict (deontic) sense, but rather *define* an object or activity (such as a card game), setting what counts as a valid movement in that game, or under which conditions one of the players wins the game, for instance. If someone does not follow the game’s rules, we would not say that she has violated a duty or obligation, but simply that she has made an invalid/illegal movement according to the rules of the game, or that she is just *not playing* that game. To consider the set of rules of the card game as analogous of a normative moral or legal system requires making a rather forced interpretation of those rules, as it would require them to be understood as they establish the ‘obligation’ or the ‘prohibition’ to win the hand.
- 43 (3.1.2) Even under a forced interpretation of the rules of the card game as prescriptive norms, we would reach the conclusion that this “normative system” is inconsistent, as it reveals the same problem as Alchourrón’s previous example. For the sake of simplicity and to avoid the necessity of a longer explanation, consider the system from the point of view of one of the players. Here, the elements of the UP would be, first, that the drawn card is a black one (or its absence, a non-black one, that is, a red card), and second, that the value of one of the cards drawn by the player is higher than that of the other player (and its absence, that the value of the other player’s card is higher or the same value). If we ignore, for the sake of simplicity (and also because the system does not provide an explicit solution for those situations) the case in which both cards are of the same value, then we have a UC with a total of four (2^2) possible generic cases:

1) the card is black and of a higher value; 2) the card is black and of a lower value; 3) the card is red and of a higher value; and 4) the card is red and of a lower value.

- 44 In this context, all instances of generic cases 2 or 3 (that is, when one player draws a black card of a lower value than the opponent's red card, or when she draws a red card of a higher value than the opponent's) would be simultaneously linked to the 'obligation' and the 'prohibition' of the same 'action' (win the hand), and hence, there would be an antinomy, which renders the system as inconsistent.
- 45 (3.1.3) Despite this, Marcus' argument is that the system is not inconsistent because the rules are *obeyable*—there are logically possible worlds in which the situation in which a black card of a lower value than a red card never arises. This makes it necessary to analyse Marcus' concept of 'obeyability'. Marcus uses the term "obeyable", but she also uses "satisfiable", apparently as a synonym. Although she offers no explicit definitions of these terms, they can be taken to mean something along the lines of 'suitability for being obeyed or satisfied', that is, they refer to the possibility of following a norm or acting as the norm prescribes (doing what it imposes or permits). The concept can in this sense be likened to that of 'complying with' or 'obeying' a norm. In this way, a set or system of norms S can be said to be obeyable if, and only if, it is possible to do everything that S prescribes,⁴⁵ that is, if it is possible to (jointly) follow all the norms contained in S for each of its generic cases.⁴⁶
- 46 Also, it seems that for a norm to be obeyable (followable, satisfiable, etc.), its conditions of application must obtain.⁴⁷ Using an example from von Wright, for the norm "Close the door" to operate and be followable, there must be a door and it must be open (this must be the case as a matter of conceptual necessity). In the same way, for the norm "Drivers approaching an intersection are required to stop their vehicles if the traffic light is red", it must be the case that (a) the agent to whom the norm applies is driving a vehicle, (b) there is an intersection with a stoplight, and (c) the stoplight is red. Otherwise, if any of the conditions (a) through (c) are not satisfied, the norm becomes irrelevant in the sense that it does not (and cannot) deontically guide the agent's behaviour.⁴⁸
- 47 In light of the foregoing, Marcus's card-game example becomes problematic. Even if the rules "Black cards trump red cards" and "Higher-valued cards trump lower-valued cards" could properly be considered genuine prescriptive norms, for them to be jointly (i.e., both simultaneously) obeyable there needs to be a situation in which a black card turns up next to a higher-valued red card. Only under these circumstances are both norms jointly applicable, and in all logically possible worlds in which these circumstances come to pass, a normative conflict will arise, making this set of norms non-satisfiable. So, in sum, Marcus's card game would indeed be an example of a non-obeyable set of rules, rather than an obeyable one.
- 48 But there is another alternative way in which the argument Marcus makes for the obeyability thesis might be interpreted. Marcus could be taken to mean that a norm or set of norms is obeyable so long as it is possible for it not to be disobeyed or broken. In this sense, the rules of the card game are 'obeyable' insofar as it could logically be the case that no red cards with a value higher than that of a black card ever turn up. As she puts it: "It is possible that the cards be so distributed that, when a black card is paired with a red card, the black card happens to be of equal or higher value".⁴⁹ This would imply that even if a set of norms is logically inconsistent, it remains obeyable whenever its conditions of application are not met. Let us suppose, for example, that an authority

enacts norms N_1 , “Hunting unicorns is prohibited” and N_2 , “Hunting unicorns is allowed”, and both norms belong to the same normative system. Despite the obvious inconsistency, these two norms could be deemed ‘obeyable’ without giving rise to any conflict, in virtue of the fact that there are no unicorns in our world, so they cannot be disobeyed; their conditions of application cannot, in our world, ever be met.

49 In short, on this interpretation, Marcus’s view would be tantamount to saying that in a normative system N_i formed by norms ‘ $p \rightarrow O(q)$ ’ and ‘ $p \rightarrow \neg O(q)$ ’, those norms are obeyable insofar as it is logically possible for there to be a world in which circumstance ‘ p ’ never occurs. Of course, in such a world no conflict would arise as far as ‘ p ’ is concerned. Despite those norms not being logically contradictory, as long as they belong to the same normative system, there is an antinomy in every generic case that contains the property ‘ p ’, rendering the normative system inconsistent. However, the generic case ‘ p ’ might be empirically void, and no conflict would then arise. As Hansson points out, whether a normative conflict or dilemma will arise depends not only on which norms have been put in place, but also on the circumstances that come to pass: “A moral dilemma will occur if and only if the moral code and the actual circumstances combine to create an incompatible set of obligations”.⁵⁰ It seems that this is the idea behind Marcus’ concept of ‘obeyability’, but the point is whether it is a reasonable one and should be preferred over another alternative concept that requires the conditions of application to be met to render a norm as ‘obeyable’.

50 As with any stipulation, it is not in itself incorrect to ascribe a particular meaning to a word or expression, such as ‘obeyability’. But stipulations can also be evaluated externally by considering whether they are reasonable or coherent with other elements. In that sense, claiming that two incompatible norms are obeyable simply because their conditions of application cannot arise (e.g., it cannot happen that we get a red card of higher value than a black card) is like saying that the two-member set of propositions “Snow is white” and “Snow is not white” is not false because it is logically possible for there to be a world with no snow. But just as there are no logically possible worlds in which that propositional set is true, there are no logically possible worlds in which those rules are jointly applicable and satisfiable, so a conflict necessarily arises. This is what makes Marcus’s stipulation quite odd.

3.2 The single-principle thesis

51 Marcus also argues that no inconsistency is needed between moral (or normative, in general) principles to give rise to a normative conflict, since such a conflict can be generated out of a *single principle*.⁵¹ If we make two incompatible promises, for example, that is enough to create a conflict,⁵² and this shows that a system’s inconsistency is not necessary, since a principle cannot be incompatible with itself unless it is self-contradictory.

52 Marcus’s claim seems sound, and if correct, it would show that there is the possibility for conflicts to arise without the need for an inconsistent system. However, things are a bit more complex than it may seem at first sight because there is an ambiguity that needs to be highlighted when talking about ‘incompatible’ promises. Two or more promises can be incompatible in a logical sense (they can be contradictory) when the promised acts or courses of conduct are logically exclusive. If an agent promises to do ‘ p ’ and later promises to do ‘ $\neg p$ ’, a normative inconsistency obtains, since we get the

result 'O(p)' and 'O-(p)', which entails 'O(p) & -O(p)'. The same happens when two acts are different but one logically entails the negation of the other (they are not logically independent). In that case, it could still be argued that the conflict is a consequence of a logical inconsistency, though it could equally be argued that this is not because of a flaw in the normative system, since the incompatible obligations are grounded in one and the same principle. On the other hand, the argument seems stronger when the different acts are incompatible strictly on account of empirical circumstances, and this is a possibility that Marcus seems to indeed contemplate.⁵³ Here, we would get a conflict without any kind of logical inconsistency within the system.

- 53 We can think of other situations of this kind in the *legal* realm as well. Most, if not all, legal systems establish a buyer's obligation to pay a seller, that is, to pay the price for the goods sold. Under this single precept, someone might simultaneously be the buyer in two contracts of sale but may lack the money needed to satisfy their obligations under both contracts, such that paying the price agreed under one contract would prevent them from paying the price agreed to under the other, and vice versa. Here, the fact of not having enough money is a strictly empirical circumstance, not a logical inconsistency of the system, nor does it flow from any logical incompatibility between the two obligations. This is an example of what Rodríguez calls "instantiation conflicts," in which we find ourselves in a situation of normative conflict that cannot be set down to an inconsistency of the normative system.⁵⁴ And such situations do not seem to be necessarily based on any single norm: They can also arise where *several norms of a consistent system* apply to an agent and yet, owing to *empirical* circumstances, the agent cannot jointly comply with them, as when someone owes the government income taxes *and* owes money under a contract of sale and yet cannot meet both of those obligations because of the lack of the financial resources to do so.⁵⁵
- 54 If we accept the possibility of dilemmas arising from strictly empirical circumstances, we could deny the conceptual link between inconsistencies in the normative system and normative conflicts as a necessary condition, which was Marcus's main thesis, despite the problems highlighted in regard to her argument for the 'obeyability' thesis.

4 Conflicts as inconsistencies and conflicts as a result of system inconsistencies

- 55 An argument has just been outlined for the view that not every normative conflict is conceptually linked to a logical inconsistency. But there are some philosophers who insist on the existence of such a conceptual link. Indeed, one interesting and well-known argument that comes out of the discussion on moral dilemmas is that implicit in any moral (or indeed any normative, in general) reasoning are two supplementary premises that give rise to a contradiction. The first lies in the Kantian or voluntarist principle that 'ought' implies 'can'. This means that no action can be morally obligatory unless it can actually be carried out (we cannot be obligated to do that which cannot be done, or which we are powerless to do), which entails that if an action is morally obligatory then it must be the case that the action can be carried out: it is possible to do so. The possibility dealt with here is empirical (not just logical) and is usually understood in the strong sense, as a *contingent* behaviour,⁵⁶ including both the possibility of *doing* the action and the possibility of *refraining from* it. This Kantian

principle can be formally expressed as the voluntarist principle, which usually takes the following form (where the symbol ‘ \diamond ’ means ‘it is possible that’):

$$O(\alpha) \rightarrow \diamond(\alpha)$$

- 56 The second premise consists in the agglomeration principle, or ‘factoring principle’. This is a theorem in deontic logic, similar to addition in propositional logic, according to which the premises ‘ $O(\alpha)$ ’ and ‘ $O(\beta)$ ’ entail ‘ $O(\alpha \ \& \ \beta)$ ’, formally expressed as follows:

$$O(\alpha) \ \& \ O(\beta) \rightarrow O(\alpha \ \& \ \beta)$$

- 57 If we combine these two premises with the premises of a ‘standard’ normative-conflict situation,⁵⁷ where an agent ought to do ‘p’ and ‘q’ and it is impossible to do ‘p & q’, we get the following reasoning, which with very slight variations we can find in different authors, such as Williams,⁵⁸ McConnell,⁵⁹ or Brink,⁶⁰ among others:

(1)	$O(p)$	\
(2)	$O(q)$	(moral conflict)
(3)	$\neg\diamond(p \ \& \ q)$	/
(4)	$(O(p) \ \& \ O(q)) \rightarrow O(p \ \& \ q)$	(1,2; agglomeration)
(5)	$O(p \ \& \ q)$	(1, 2, 4; addition, <i>modus ponens</i>)
(6)	$O(p \ \& \ q) \rightarrow \diamond(p \ \& \ q)$	(5; voluntarist principle)
(7)	$\diamond(p \ \& \ q)$	(5, 6; <i>modus ponens</i>)
(8)	$\diamond(p \ \& \ q) \ \& \ \neg\diamond(p \ \& \ q)$	(3, 7; addition) – INCONSISTENCY

- 58 So, in these authors’ views, this demonstrates that every situation of conflict entails a contradiction. However, two considerations need to be considered here. First, there is a lot of philosophical debate around the Kantian and agglomeration principles, which are far from being uncontroversial or universally accepted. Second, and more relevant to the discussion, even accepting the former argument, this only shows that a normative conflict can be *reconstructed* or represented as a logical contradiction. *The reasoning does not in any way show that normative conflicts are owed exclusively to inconsistencies within a normative system*, that is, to logical incompatibilities between the system’s elements (its principles, rules, directives, etc.). Indeed, as discussed, it could be the case that two *consistent* norms of the system lead to a conflict when combined with certain empirical circumstances, and in such a case the conflict would not be a consequence of an inconsistent normative system, even if, with certain additional premises, the conflict can be *represented* as an inconsistency.

- 59 In that sense, I have elsewhere⁶¹ offered to explain how a consistent normative system of two or more norms can lead to a normative contradiction and conflict. Proceeding from the distinction between *generic* and *individual* actions,⁶² I argue that a conflict

arises whenever a single individual act can be subsumed under two different generic actions, which the system qualifies with two different and incompatible deontic operators in two different (and logically compatible) norms, such that the individual act at once satisfies one of the norms and violates the other (hence the conflict). If no alternative courses of action are available that can satisfy all applicable norms, the conflict may prove to be unsolvable, but not because of a logical inconsistency in the normative system, despite the fact the conflict arises for logical or conceptual reasons.

⁶³

- 60 Consider the following example, consisting of a very basic moral system with just two principles: (1) It is obligatory to keep promises; and (2) it is forbidden to harm innocent people. The generic acts ‘keeping promises’ and ‘harming the innocent’ are logically independent, as it is logically possible to do any of the following at the same time: (a) keep the promise and harm an innocent; (b) keep the promise and not harm an innocent; (c) not to keep the promise and harm an innocent; or (d) not to keep the promise and not harm an innocent. The two generic actions are deontically qualified with different operators: obligation and prohibition. As the contents of the norms are logically independent, there is no inconsistency between them—they could be represented as ‘O(p)’ and ‘Ph(q)’, for example. Even so, it is both logically and empirically possible for a single individual act to simultaneously fulfil a promise and harm an innocent person (i.e., an individual action ‘a’ can be an instance of both the generic action ‘p’ and the generic action ‘q’). In that case, this individual act would be both permitted (as per norm 1) and forbidden (as per norm 2) under this basic moral system. And if no alternative actions are available for the agent, and the only possible way to keep the promise is by harming an innocent person, then we face a normative conflict, even within a consistent system.⁶⁴

5 Conclusion

- 61 The foregoing analysis seems to support the conclusion that the existence of logical inconsistencies within normative systems is a *sufficient* condition for a normative conflict. Whenever two or more inconsistent norms are jointly applicable, a normative conflict will necessarily arise, since these conflicts mean precisely that we cannot (jointly) comply with both or all of these norms. That is so even if one of the affected norms is a permission, provided we assume the concept of normative conflict proposed in this article (as seems reasonable if we assume that permissive norms give agents a legitimate expectation that their action under such norms is legally or morally justified). As discussed, however, it also appears that some conflictual situations are to be attributed not to *system* inconsistencies but to strictly empirical constraints, suggesting that even if logical consistency is relevant and can limit the incidence of conflict situations, it cannot on its own guarantee an absence of such situations. So, in conclusion, normative conflicts and dilemmas appear to be an inescapable feature of our legal and moral practices, in the sense that even in perfectly consistent normative systems, there is no way of excluding the possibility for a conflict to arise.

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NOTES

1. I am not referring to situations in which the requirements of a legal system are incompatible with those of a moral system (where the legal system requires or permits something that is incompatible with a moral requirement or permission, or vice versa), but to situations of incompatibility arising *within the same* normative system.
 2. A good overview of this debate can be found in Gowans 1987, and in Mason 1996.
 3. An example of this view can be found in Donagan 1987; 1996.
 4. This, of course, refers only to the mainstream position. For a quite different view, see for instance, Chiassoni 2007: ch. 7.
 5. Of course, the very idea of such a link presupposes that norms (understood as prescriptions) are bound by logical or deductive relationships that can be explained and analysed through a proper model of deontic logic. This is a contested issue that cannot be addressed here, but it will be assumed for the sake of the argument put forward in this paper.
 6. Whether this can actually be done, given our limitations and the complexity of the situations our normative systems have to deal with, is another question.
 7. Not in the sense that conflicts or dilemmas will necessarily arise *as a matter of fact*, but in the sense that it is an unavoidable feature, like the ‘fragility’ of glass: It might never break, but it will break if certain conditions are met, and there’s no way to eradicate this fragility.
 8. In that sense, inconsistency might be said to be a *sufficient* (but not a necessary) condition for conflicts, such that eliminating all normative inconsistencies within a system would make it possible to eliminate all the conflicts owed to those inconsistencies.
 9. For an overview of the different conceptions and classifications of the term “normative conflict” as used by different authors in legal theory, see Huerta Ochoa 2003: 68–76. Some authors even use “normative conflict” and “normative inconsistency” as synonyms, such as Elhag, Breuker & Brouwer (1999).
 10. The author defines “the *subject* (or subjects) of a prescription” as “the agent (or agents), to whom the prescription is addressed or given” (von Wright 1963: 77).
 11. I believe that this would be acceptable to most moral and legal philosophers. In legal theory, this notion is compatible with many definitions of “antinomy”, such as those covered in Mazzaresse (1989: 347). With greater precision, Celotto (1997: 116) defines “antinomy” as “a situation of incompatibility between two norms that set forth different and incompatible legal consequences in one and the same case, such that application of one excludes application of the other” (my translation), where ‘case’ renders the Italian word *fattispecie*, equivalent to the German *Tatbestand*, meaning ‘fact-type’, a category of facts or class of situations (e.g., trespass) to which a norm applies.
 12. A key element in this analysis is the concept of *compliance*, since conflict is defined in terms of the impossibility of joint compliance with all the norms applicable to a given case. Like the concept of effectiveness, compliance depends on the truth-value of the propositional content connected to the norm (prescription). Thus, given the prescription ‘S ought to do A’, S is compliant with it if, and only if, the connected proposition ‘S does (or has done) A’ is true, and she is not compliant if the proposition is false. In a normative conflict, the situation is such that the subject cannot empirically make true the set of propositions connected to all the norms applicable to the case.
- Although in legal theory a distinction is drawn between *compliance*, which only requires outward behaviour consistent with a norm (an objective or external element), and *obedience*, which additionally demands a certain attitude of acceptance on the agent’s part, we need not dig into these details for our analysis. The only relevant concept here is that of *compliance*, which is also entailed by *obedience*. In a more technical definition, a normative subject is said to *comply* with norm N if, and only if, her behaviour makes true the propositional content connected to it. For a

more technical and formalized definition, see Moreso & Navarro 1996: 115. For the distinction between the two concepts, see also Hernández Marín 1998: 254-258. The distinction could also be assimilated to Hart's distinction between the "external point of view" (akin to compliance) and the "internal point of view" (akin to obedience). See Hart 1961.

13. The classic example is Kant 1991 [1797]: 50. In the same vein, see Lemmon 1965; Davidson 1991.

14. Marcus 1980.

15. Here I will be treating 'normative contradiction' and 'deontic contradiction' synonymously. Some authors, such as Huerta Ochoa (2003: 50-59), distinguish between deontic contradictions (where two norms are identical in their content, and yet are incompatible in their deontic character, in von Wright's terms) and logical contradictions (where the norms' deontically qualified contents are logically incompatible). In this way, for instance, we would have a *deontic* contradiction if a system were to regulate one and the same case with solutions 'O(p)' and '¬O(p)', and a *logical* contradiction if the solutions were 'O(p)' and 'O¬(p)'.

However, in standard models of deontic logic, like the ones used by von Wright (1951), Hanson (1965), and Alchourrón and Bulygin (1971), this distinction becomes idle. For in virtue of the rules of deontic logic, every case of deontic contradiction can be turned into a logical contradiction, and vice versa. For instance, given that 'O(p)' entails 'P(p)', and also that '¬O(p)' is equivalent to 'P¬(p)', the deontic contradiction 'O(p) ∧ ¬O(p)' entails the logical contradiction 'P(p) ∧ P¬(p)'. Similarly, since 'O¬(p)' is equivalent to '¬P(p)', the logical contradiction 'O(p) ∧ O¬(p)' entails the deontic contradiction 'P(p) ∧ ¬P(p)'. For this reason, I think it is better to have a unified treatment of cases of inconsistency according to a standard model of deontic logic.

16. I am here using Alchourrón and Bulygin's (1971: 62-63) definition, according to which "[A] normative system α is *inconsistent* in a case C_i of a UC_j if α correlates C_i with two or more solutions in such a way that the conjunction of these solutions is a deontic contradiction". Under this definition, there's no difference, from a deontic logic perspective, between 'impossible obligations' [the obligation of doing something logically impossible, such as 'O(a ∧ ¬a)'] and 'conflicting obligations' [mutually incompatible obligations, such as 'O(a) ∧ O(¬a)'], because both formulae collapse in a standard system of deontic logic. Faroldi, Ghari, Lehmann, and Studer (2024) propose a model of *justification deontic logic* (with statements of the type 't : A', that can be read as 't justifies the obligation of A'), which distinguishes impossible obligations (which are excluded for logical reasons) from conflicting obligations, as no reason or set of reasons can justify doing the logically impossible, but a reason or set of reasons (legal or moral) may provide both a justification for doing something and also for not doing so. This raises very interesting philosophical questions, even though they will not be treated here.

17. Alchourrón 1981: 133.

18. These kinds of situations are what Alf Ross calls a "partial-partial antinomy" (Ross 1958: 129).

19. See, Alchourrón & Bulygin 1971.

20. See, for example, Guastini 1998.

21. See, Feis 2020.

22. I will return to this question when commenting on Marcus's position in section 3.1.

23. Among others, Munzer 1973; Hilpinen 1985; Hamner Hill 1987; Lindhal 1992.

24. One example is Hernández Marín (1998: 255-256) who argues: "An individual z is *compliant* with a prescription P if, and only if, the following two conditions are met: (1) There is something that z is obliged to do under P , and (2) z does everything he or she is obliged to do under P . An individual z is *non-compliant* with (in violation of) a prescription P if, and only if, the following two circumstances hold: (1) There is something that z is obliged to do under P , and (2) z does not do everything he or she is obliged to do under P ." Consequently, "if there is nothing an individual z is obliged to do under a prescription P , then z is neither compliant nor non-compliant with P ... or, to put it another way, being obliged to do something under a prescription is a necessary

condition both for complying with the prescription and for failing to comply with it.” (my translation).

However, it is difficult to pin down Hernández Marín’s exact position. For one thing, he explicitly rejects the conception of the law as a deductive system built on logical connections between norms (Hernández Marín 2003). For this reason, he cannot strictly be said to be committed to the view that certain system contradictions or inconsistencies give rise to conflicts, since he would outright reject the idea of ‘inconsistency’ in a legal system. For another thing, as far as I know, the position I am here attributing to him is not one he has explicitly set out but has been reconstructed from certain parts of his work that bear on this issue and from personal conversations I have had with him.

25. As Hamner Hill puts it (1987: 230), “permissory norms are not the sort of norms with which a norm-subject can meaningfully be said to comply or fail to comply.”

26. According to a standard model of deontic logic, for the case where the system contains a single action ‘p’, the deontic solution ‘O(p)’ is equivalent to ‘P(p) \wedge \neg P(\neg p)’.

27. Given that each of the behaviours being regulated is logically independent of the others, the total number of behaviours can be determined by the formula ‘2ⁿ’, where ‘n’ is the number of actions/omissions.

28. The deontic operator ‘F’ (facultative) is equivalent to a behaviour and its contradictory behaviour both being permitted. For instance, if the action ‘smoking’ is facultative, then both smoking and not smoking are permitted.

29. Among others, Munzer 1973; Hilpinen 1985; Hamner Hill 1987; Lindhal 1992.

30. This is a view that von Wright (1963: 144) also seems hold, for in turning to the question of the consistency of a set or system of norms, he treats mandates and permissions differently: “a set of commands and permissions is consistent (the norms are compatible) if, and only if, it is logically possible, under any given condition of application, to obey *all* the commands collectively and avail oneself of *each one* of the permissions individually which apply on that condition”. Obligations and prohibitions, then, are norms we *obey* (or which we associate with ‘obedience’, a term that, for the sake of simplicity, I am treating as synonymous with ‘compliance’); permissions, by contrast, are norms we *make use of*, *avail ourselves of*, *benefit from*, and so on.

I think this highlights a relevant difference in the context of the justification of behaviours according to norms. There are certain kinds of norms that impede the justification of whichever behaviours are incompatible with their normative content (for instance, the obligation to stop in front of a traffic light in red impedes the justification of not stopping, or the prohibition of smoking -obligation of not to smoke- impedes the justification of smoking), but this is not the case with permissions.

31. This doesn’t necessarily make the behaviour optional for the agent. For it may turn out that the open course of conduct in question is the *only* ‘open door’, that is, the only deontically possible alternative, as happens with obligations.

32. Hernández Marín 1998: 249–250. In so doing, however, he commits to the view that for each prescriptive statement there can only be one corresponding assertive statement.

33. Hernández Marín 1998: 250.

34. Moreso & Navarro 1996.

35. See, von Wright 1963: 37.

36. Von Wright (1983: 139) frames the idea in terms of satisfaction rather than effectiveness, as follows: “I shall say that a permissive norm is satisfiable if, and only if, it is possible that the permitted state of affairs obtains at *some* time in the history of the norm. And it is satisfied if, and only if, at some time in its history that which it permits actually is also the case.”

37. A deontically perfect world is one in which all norms are always effective. This concept was coined Hintikka (1971) and is also adopted by Moreso and Navarro (1996). It is true that, as these authors point out, the concept of effectiveness seems far too demanding, since a single case of

non-compliance will render a norm ineffective. But this is the same problem we have with the concept of truth: If we take a proposition like “Summers in Bermuda are hot”, it only takes a single summer in Bermuda in which the temperature doesn’t get hot to make that proposition false, even if the vast majority of those summers are indeed hot. Consequently—and similar to the way we ‘relax’ the concept of truth to accommodate the *mostly* true, making it possible for generic propositions to be considered true even if they do not always correspond to reality but do so on *most* occasions—we could rely on a ‘relaxed’ concept of effectiveness to accommodate norms that may not always achieve compliance but do so on most occasions (by and large) or on a majority of occasions (more often than not), making it possible to consider norms effective when the corresponding (assertive) propositions are true *most* of the time, or even *much* of the time, though not *all* of the time. Another possibility explored by the authors is the use of ‘most (of)’, ‘much (of)’, and other such determiners as heterodox quantifiers, an idea initially put forward by Platts (1979).

38. This distinction has also been pointed out by Donagan (1987: 285–286; 1996: 13).

39. This could be the basis for the second-order regulative moral principle defended by Marcus (1980: 121), expressed as: “as rational agents with some control of our lives and institutions, we ought to conduct our lives and arrange our institutions so as to minimize predicaments of moral conflict.”. The same idea is reiterated in Marcus (1996: 23). But the idea that we should avoid moral conflicts or dilemmas, and should do so on moral grounds, is not a foregone conclusion and has indeed been called into question. See, Hansson 1998.

40. Marcus 1980; 1996.

41. After Marcus, some other philosophers also came to this view. See, for instance, Hilpinen (1985: 193–94): “It is important to note that a system of norms need not be formally inconsistent to generate normative conflicts: the conflicts may depend on contingent circumstances—on the agent’s past actions or on circumstances which are beyond the agent’s control ... The formal consistency of a normative system does not ensure more than minimal quandary-freedom.” See also Rescher (1987: 30): “(E)thical dilemmas need not result from a *conflict of rules*. A single rule ... can suffice to generate the problem, without any collision between discrepant rules.”

42. Marcus 1980: 128.

43. Marcus 1980: 129.

44. Von Wright 1963: 6–7.

45. “Possible”, in this context, refers to *logical* possibility, regardless of the way empirical circumstances may affect compliance.

46. And thus make true all the propositions linked to the norms in S.

47. On conditions of application, see von Wright 1963: 73–76.

48. Other examples could be, for instance, the norm “Parents must feed their children” with regard to people who have no children, or the norm “Judges must decide their cases according to the Law”, with respect to anyone who is not a judge. It would be quite odd to claim that those norms are ‘obeyable’ for those people or that they ‘obey’ them.

49. Marcus 1980: 129.

50. Hansson 1998: 410.

51. Marcus 1980: 125.

52. The single principle at play here is of course that promises must be kept. However, not all moral principles seem apt to give rise to conflicts. A case in point would be a moral obligation to always tell the truth, since propositions, if true, are necessarily compatible (so there are no two truths that we can speak of that will give rise to a normative conflict under this single principle).

53. “Under the single principle of promise keeping, I might make two promises in all good faith and reason that they will not conflict, but then they do, as a result of circumstances that were unpredictable and beyond my control” (Marcus 1980: 125).

54. Rodríguez 2002: 99–100.

55. Even though, the possibility of ‘instantiation conflicts’ due to strict empirical conditions is not uncontroversial and has been challenged by Sardo (2018), who claims that those situations can be reframed as antinomies between general cases.

56. See for instance Muffato (2010), who poses strong reasons to interpret it as a ‘strong’ possibility (contingency).

57. Although normative conflicts are typically presented as situations involving colliding mandates, we saw in section 2 that there are reasons why the notion should be extended to include conflicts between mandates and permissions.

58. Williams 1973: 180.

59. McConnell 1978: 271.

60. Brink 1996: 108.

61. In Martínez Zorrilla 2011.

62. Von Wright 1963: 35–37.

63. I use the label “contextual antinomies” to refer to those situations; both to distinguish them from “classic” antinomies (inconsistencies in the normative system) and for stressing the fact that, despite dealing with consistent norms, the conflict arises for logical or conceptual reasons (and hence they are predictable₁, although not predictable₂), contrary to the ‘instantiation conflicts’, which respond exclusively to empirical or factual circumstances (so they are not predictable₁ nor predictable₂).

Guglielmo Feis (2020) challenges this view, questioning the idea that contextual antinomies and instantiation conflicts are actually different categories, as in both cases the existence of a conflict depends on certain empirical facts and not on the logical properties of the normative system. Nevertheless, in my opinion the distinction is relevant and makes sense, for the following reasons:

In contextual antinomies, there is no logical inconsistency between, for instance, ‘O(p)’ and ‘Ph(q)’, being ‘p’ and ‘q’ logically independent actions, but it can be assured that under certain situation ‘c’, being ‘c’ an individual action subsumable under both ‘p’ and ‘q’, we obtain as a consequence ‘P(c)’ and ‘¬P(c)’, which leads to a conflict for logical reasons. In other words, the conflict is conceptually predictable (or predictable₁). The criticism that ‘c’ refers to specific empirical circumstances and not to a logical category may be avoided exchanging ‘c’ for “whichever individual actions subsumable in ‘p’ and ‘q’”.

If we take instead the example of the two debts, and we represent the obligation of agent A to pay her debt to creditor X as ‘O(p)’, and the obligation to pay the debt to creditor Y as ‘O(q)’, we also acknowledge that ‘O(p)’ and ‘O(q)’ are logically independent and there is no logical inconsistency of any kind. But contrary to contextual antinomies, there will be no conflict in the hypothetical case that some individual action ‘c’ is simultaneously subsumable both in ‘p’ and ‘q’ (for example, if X has acquired Y’s credit rights). Hence, the conflict does *not* depend on the condition that the same individual action is subsumable under both generic actions (moreover, if this is the case, it won’t be ever a conflict!). The conflict will depend solely on certain additional factual and unpredictable₂ (and most likely also unpredictable₁) circumstances, such as A’s financial resources being limited to the extent that satisfying either of the debts impedes the satisfaction of the other. That is, only in certain situations will there be a conflict, and this will not depend on the logical structure of the normative system, nor is it predictable in a conceptual sense.

64. Nevertheless, in more cases than could be expected at first glance, situations of conflict may arise from the fact that the incompatible actions ‘p’ and ‘q’ are not really (conceptually or logically) independent. In a classic example of such moral conflict from the literature, we are on our way to an appointment (and thus have an obligation deriving from a promise) when we come upon an unattended victim of a road accident (and thus come under a concurrent obligation to lend emergency assistance). Although making it to our appointment on time and giving emergency assistance (before any first responders reach the scene) are two logically independent

courses of action, they cannot, in the given circumstances, be carried out jointly (at the same time), since they require us to be at different places at the same time, which is logically as well as empirically impossible (at least in our world). On this question see, for example, Ayer 1971: 71–87; Hospers 1967: 216–227.

To determine if two or more actions are logically independent, we should consider what Alchourrón and Bulygin refer to as the “obligatoriness principle” (Alchourrón & Bulygin 1984: 159) or Brink as the “obligation execution principle” (Brink 1996: 111). Alchourrón and Bulygin express the principle in this way: “Under x ’s orders, it is obligatory to carry out all the actions that are logically necessary to satisfy all the obligations established under x ’s orders (= all the obligations that are logical consequences of the set of propositions of the action ordered by x)” (Alchourrón & Bulygin 1984: 159, my translation). That is, an obligation to carry out an action also entails an obligation to do whatever follows as a logical consequence of that action. Brink seems to refer to the same idea when he states that if we have an obligation to do ‘ a ’, and we would be prevented from doing ‘ a ’ if we did ‘ b ’, we have an obligation not to do ‘ b ’. This can be formally expressed as follows:

$$(O(a) \wedge (b \rightarrow \neg a)) \rightarrow O\neg(b)$$

Or, in a logically equivalent form:

$$(O(a) \wedge (a \rightarrow \neg b)) \rightarrow O\neg(b)$$

So, in cases where we have two obligations, such as ‘ $O(p)$ ’ and ‘ $O(q)$ ’, but ‘ q ’ entails ‘ $\neg p$ ’, we actually would face a conflict for logical or conceptual reasons, but not due to the specific empirical facts of the case.

It is not always easy, though, to determine the absence of logical independence between deontically regulated behaviours, which makes it difficult to see whether the problem is logical or empirical. A curious example can be found in Gavazzi (1959: 64 ff), an example in turn taken from Cicero, wherein we have a norm that rewards the killing of a tyrant (if someone kills a tyrant, the killer shall be granted anything they request), and another norm that states that if someone kills a tyrant, the judges must sentence the killer’s five closest relatives to death). Alexander, the tyrant of Pherae in Thessaly, is killed by his wife, who as her reward demands the freedom of the sons she has had with her husband. Under one norm her sons are to be released from death, while under the other they are to be executed (for they are the tyrant’s closest relatives). Gavazzi claims that although some authors regard this as an *empirically unique* case—there can only be one such case, and that is due to its circumstances—what we are in fact looking at is a partial-partial antinomy under Alf Ross’s classification (see footnote 18), and so a *logical* contradiction between *norms*. I would argue that while Gavazzi is right to see this as a logical problem, it is not a partial-partial antinomy, since the case regulated by the two norms is exactly the same one (the killing of a tyrant). What we have here, in my view, is a lack of logical independence between the regulated actions, since one of them contains an absolute universalization (“anything requested”) and therefore logically includes the other (“killing the closest relatives”). So, even if this cannot be a conflict owed strictly to empirical circumstances, it seems quite problematic to treat it under Ross’s classification.

ABSTRACTS

This paper examines the relation between an inconsistent normative system and normative conflicts so as to determine whether the former is a necessary and/or a sufficient condition for

the latter or, stated otherwise, whether a perfectly consistent normative system could guarantee the absence of normative conflicts and dilemmas. The traditional thesis that moral conflicts arise from inconsistencies or formal flaws within a normative system has been already challenged by some philosophers. Specifically, for Ruth B. Marcus, conflicts and dilemmas may arise even within the frame of a logically consistent system. Here, I analyse the connections between consistency and the phenomenon of normative conflicts, paying special attention to Marcus's main arguments for the conclusion that normative conflicts may arise not only as a necessary consequence of an inconsistent system but also within the frame of a consistent one. In so doing, however, I show that it does not happen for the exact reasons she offers.

O povezavi med konsistenco in konfliktom v normativnih sistemih. Ta članek preučuje razmerje med konsistentnim normativnim sistemom in normativnimi konflikti, da bi ugotovil, ali je prvi nujen in/ali zadosten pogoj za druge ali, drugače povedano, ali bi popolnoma konsistenten normativni sistem lahko zagotovil odsotnost normativnih konfliktov in dilem. Tradicionalno tezo, da moralni konflikti izhajajo iz nekonsistence ali formalnih pomanjkljivosti znotraj normativnega sistema, so nekateri filozofi že izpodbijali. Zlasti za Ruth B. Marcus lahko konflikti in dileme nastanejo tudi v okviru logično konsistentnega sistema. V tem prispevku avtor analizira povezave med konsistenco in pojavom normativnih konfliktov, pri čemer posebno pozornost nameni Marcusovim glavnim argumentom za sklep, da normativni konflikti lahko nastanejo ne le kot nujna posledica nekonsistentnega sistema, ampak tudi v okviru konsistentnega sistema. Pri tem pa avtor pokaže, da se to ne zgodi iz tistih razlogov, ki jih je navajala Marcusova.

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motsclessl normativni konflikti, moralne dileme, antinomije, deontična logika, normativni sistemi

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AUTHOR

DAVID MARTÍNEZ ZORRILLA

 IDREF : <https://idref.fr/12876094X>

 VIAF : <http://viaf.org/viaf/90652899>

 ISNI : <https://isni.org/isni/0000000116843289>

 BnF BNF : <http://data.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cb16644463t>

Associate Professor of Philosophy of Law, Director of the PhD Program in Law, Politics and Economics, Faculty of Law and Political Science, Open University of Catalonia

Address: Rambla del Poble Nou 156, 08018, Barcelona, Spain

E-mail: dmartinezz@uoc.edu